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The relativity of numbers

Research article

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

In this publication, some aspects of the relationship between equivalence and (the law of) identity, which is usually adduced as the first law of nature and of human thought, are considered in more detail.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The most simple rules of mathematics were used.

RESULTS:

It is necessary to distinguish between identity and equivalence. Both notions are not completely the same.

CONCLUSION:

Something can be equivalent with something other, but need not be identical with the same.

Keywords:

Identity; Equivalence; Difference; Contradiction; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

The identity of mathematical operations, mathematical definitions or of events in the real world and of other kinds of natural processes attracted the attention of scholars through centuries and are still at the centre of scientific discussion. However, what is identity, under which circumstances is something identical only with itself and not different from itself while equally different from its own other? A radical position might advocate that even identity and equivalence are identical, that there is no difference at all. However, to say that i.e. random events like y_t and x_t are identical is to say that such random events are the same. Nonetheless, we can't but notice that y_t and x_t which certain aspects might be in equivalent with each other are at the same (period of) time also different. Even something identical with itself might be different from itself. Under certain conditions of special theory of relativity, a certain path viewed from a co-moving observer is a straight line, while the same path viewed by a stationary observer at the same (period of) time is curved. It is the same **something** (i.e. the path of a falling ball on our earth) which **is both, curved and not curved** (see Barukčić, 2019) **and both is true** at the same (period of) time t . Any something is thus far in its own self a contradiction which sublates itself, a possible which appears to contain in its own self its own other. In other words, a human being, even if it is itself and remains itself, the same does not remain that what it is, itself, it changes too. The identity of a human being with itself is an identity through which there is present in a certain human being that which a certain human being is in itself, independently of any changes. Fascinating as this can and should be, it appears equally reasonably possible or even likely to wonder how can this be? Why is something the way it is, full of contradictions and still existent? How can two like y_t and x_t which are obviously different be identical with each other since both have an existence on their own? As outlined before and even if still at the centre of non-ending scientific debates, identity seems to many to be more or less in itself completely unproblematic because it is in the end the relationship that everything has to itself and to nothing else - what could be less problematic than that? In point of fact, even if identity as such is the identity of identity and non-identity, it seems entirely plausible that there appears to be a need for a more courageous distinction between identity and equivalence. Equivalence which is undividedly present in identity as an inseparable element of identity is different from identity. Entirely in this sense, even mathematical operations, mathematical definitions, things or events in the real world and other kind of natural processes can be more or less equivalent with each other but need not be identical.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

The numbers do not exist in and for themselves but are related to objective reality in this or that way. Some aspects of numbers, their relationship to themselves and to other numbers have been revisited in this research.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. The number +0

Definition 2.1 (The number +0). Let c denote the speed of light in vacuum (Drude, 1894; Tombe, 2015; Weber and Kohlrausch, 1856, 1857), let ϵ_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number (Bombelli, 1579). The number +0 is defined as the expression

$$+0 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv + (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) - (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \equiv 0 \times 1 \quad (1)$$

while '=' or \equiv denotes the equals sign (Recorde, 1557) or equality sign (Rolle, 1690) used to indicate equality and '-' (Widmann, 1489; Pacioli, 1494) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus (Recorde, 1557) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

Remark 2.1. Roger Cotes (1682 – 1716) (Cotes and Halley, 1714) or Leonhard Euler's (1707 – 1783) identity (Euler, 1748) is regarded as one of the most beautiful equations (Wilson, 2018). In this context, it is provisionally presumed, that Euler's identity (Euler, 1748) is logically sound and correct while the same is not investigated in detail.

2.2.2. The number +1

Definition 2.2 (The number +1). Again, let c denote the speed of light in vacuum (Drude, 1894; Tombe, 2015; Weber and Kohlrausch, 1856, 1857), let ϵ_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number (Bombelli, 1579). Based on Planck's constant (see Planck, 1901,) h and Dirac's/Schrödinger's (see also Schrödinger, Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander, 1926; Dirac and Fowler, 1926; Dirac, 1926) constant \hbar it is

$$+1 \equiv \frac{h}{2 \times \pi \times \hbar} \quad (2)$$

The number +1 is defined as the expression

$$+1 \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \equiv + (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \equiv \frac{h}{2 \times \pi \times \hbar} \quad (3)$$

while again '=' or \equiv may denote the equals sign (Recorde, 1557) or equality sign (Rolle, 1690) used to indicate equality and '-' (Widmann, 1489; Pacioli, 1494) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus (Recorde, 1557) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well. Combining equation 2 and equation 3, the natural foundation of Archimedes constant π , which is even part of the Einstein's field equations (see also Einstein, 1916), is given as

$$\pi \equiv \frac{h}{2 \times (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \times \hbar} \quad (4)$$

while h is Planck's constant (see Planck, 1901,), \hbar is Dirac's/Schrödinger's (see also Schrödinger, Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander, 1926; Dirac and Fowler, 1926; Dirac, 1926) constant.

2.2.3. The infinity

Definition 2.3 (The infinity). *Let $+\infty$ denote positive infinity. Let $-\infty$ denote negative infinity.*

John Wallis (1616-1703), an English clergyman and mathematician, contributed to the development of infinitesimal calculus. Wallis defined especially the notion of infinity.

... esto enim ∞ nota numeri infiniti ...
(see Wallis, 1655, p. 21)

Infinity may possess many properties, while only view of these properties are identified by science. However, according to third parties, Albert Einstein in particular has urged great caution in this matter.

**“Two things are infinite, the universe and human stupidity,
and I am not yet completely sure about the universe.”**
(Albert Einstein according to Perls, 1969, p. 52)

2.2.4. Basic rules for exponentiation

Definition 2.4 (View basic rules of exponentiation). *Let $n = 1 + 1 + \dots$ denote a positive integer and let x denote any real number, then x^n corresponds to repeated multiplication as*

$$x^n \equiv \underbrace{x^1 \times x^1 \times x^1 \times x^1 \dots}_{n\text{-times}} \equiv x^{1+1+1+1+\dots} \quad (5)$$

From this definition, some basic rules of exponentiation can be deduced. It is

$$x^a \times x^b \equiv x^{a+b} \quad (6)$$

or

$$(x \times y)^a \equiv x^a \times y^a \quad (7)$$

or

$$\left(\frac{x^a}{y^a}\right) = \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^a \quad (8)$$

or

$$(x^a)^b = (x^{a \times b}) = (x^b)^a \quad (9)$$

et cetera.

2.3. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to the something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*¹ too.

2.4. Axioms

Whether science needs new and obviously generally valid statements (axioms) which are able to assure the truth of theorems proved from them may remain an unanswered question. In order to be accepted, a new axiom candidate (see [Easwaran, 2008](#)) should be at least as simple as possible and logically consistent to enable advances in our knowledge of nature. The importance of axioms is particularly emphasized by Albert Einstein. “**Die wahrhaft großen Fortschritte der Naturerkenntnis sind auf einem der Induktion fast diametral entgegengesetzten Wege entstanden.**” (see [Einstein, 1919](#), p. 17). In general, *lex identitatis*, *lex contradictionis* and *lex negationis* have the potential to denote the most simple, the most general and the most far-reaching axioms of science, the foundation of our today’s and of our future scientific inquiry.

2.4.1. Principium identitatis (Axiom I)

Principium identitatis or **lex identitatis** or axiom I, is closely related to central problems of metaphysics, epistemology and of science as such. It turns out that it is more than rightful to assume that

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (10)$$

is true, otherwise there is every good reason to suppose that nothing can be discovered at all. Identity as the epitome of a self-identical or of self-reference is at the same time different from difference, identity is free from difference, identity is not difference, identity is at the same time the other of itself, identity is non-identity. Identity as simple equality with itself is determined by a non-being, by a non-being of its own other, by a non-being of difference, identity is different from difference. Identity is in its very own nature different and is in its own self the opposite of itself (symmetry). It is equally

$$-1 \equiv -1 \quad (11)$$

In general, +1 and -1 are distinguished, however these distinct are related to one and the same 1. Identity as a vanishing of otherness, therefore, is this distinguishedness in one relation. It is

$$0 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv 0 \times 1 \equiv 0 \quad (12)$$

¹Strobino, Riccardo, “Ibn Sina’s Logic”, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

2.4.2. Principium contradictionis (Axiom II)

Principium contradictionis or **lex contradictionis** ^{2, 3, 4} or axiom II, the other of *lex identitatis*, the negative of *lex identitatis*, the opposite of *lex identitatis*, a complementary of *lex identitatis*, can be expressed mathematically as

$$+0 \equiv 0 \times 1 \equiv +1 \quad (13)$$

In addition to the above, from the point of view of mathematics, axiom II (equation 13) is equally the most simple mathematical expression and formulation of a (logical) contradiction.

2.4.3. Principium negationis (Axiom III)

Lex negationis or axiom III, is often mismatched with simple opposition. However, from the point of view of philosophy and other sciences, identity, contradiction, negation and similar notions are equally mathematical descriptions of the most simple laws of objective reality. What sort of natural process is negation at the end? Mathematically, we define principium negationis or *lex negationis* or axiom III as

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times 0 \equiv \neg(0) \times 0 \equiv +1 \quad (14)$$

where \neg denotes (logical (Boole, 1854) or natural) negation (Royce, 1917; Heinemann, Fritz H., 1943; Ayer, 1952; Hedwig, 1980; Kunen, 1987; Wedin, 1990; Koch, 1999; Horn, 1989; Speranza and Horn, 2010; Förster and Melamed, 2012; Newstadt, 2015). In this context, there is some evidence that

$$\text{Negation}(1) \times 1 \equiv \neg(1) \times 1 = 0 \quad (15)$$

Logically, it follows that

$$\text{Negation}(1) \equiv 0 \quad (16)$$

²Horn, Laurence R., "Contradiction", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Winter 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2018/entries/contradiction/>.

³Barukčić I. Aristotle's law of contradiction and Einstein's special theory of relativity. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics (JDDT)*. 15Mar.2019;9(2):125-43. <https://jddtonline.info/index.php/jddt/article/view/2389>

⁴Barukčić, Ilija. (2020, December 28). The contradiction is existing objectively and real (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4396106>

3. Results

3.1. Theorem. The principle of superposition and multiplication

Theorem 1 (The principle of superposition and multiplication). *The superposition principle has been re-formulated by Daniel Bernoulli (1700 – 1782) in 1753 (“Later (1753), Daniel Bernoulli formulated the principle of superposition ...”(see Brillouin, Leon, 1946, p. 2)) too. The superposition of possible numbers or states are again possible number or states et cetera. It is equally*

$$1 \times 1 \times 1 \times \dots = 1 \quad (17)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+1 = +1 \quad (18)$$

is true. Therefore, according to our today’s rules of arithmetic, we have to accept as being equally true that

$$1 \times 1 \times 1 \times \dots = 1 \quad (19)$$

However, in order to put classical logic, number theory and other scientific disciplines on a foundation that can be verified by scientific experiments, the number 1, for example, was defined in natural constants (see equation 3, p. 8). Equation 19 becomes

$$\left(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0\right) \times \left(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0\right) \times \left(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0\right) \times \dots = \left(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0\right) \quad (20)$$

□

Numbers like +0 and +1 are the mathematical foundation of classical logic and of Boolean algebra, and might end up at the logical superposition principle. In quantum theory, the quadratic rule of quantum superposition is widely discussed.

3.2. Theorem. The principle of superposition and exponentiation

Theorem 2 (The principle of superposition and exponentiation). *The superposition principle, also known as superposition property, has many applications in physics and other sciences but applies to various conditions, including algebraic equations, linear differential equations, and potentially to numbers too. The principle of superposition from the point of view of exponentiation is given as*

$$(x_t)^{+1} \times (x_t)^{+0} = (x_t)^{+1} \quad (21)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+1 = +1 \quad (22)$$

is true. Historically, the state of superposition is a natural law, which has been stated by the Danish geologist Nicolaus Steno (1638–1686) in his 1696 book (see [Stenonis, Nicolai, 1669](#)) ‘De Solido Intra Naturaliter Contento Dissertationis Prodomus’. The principle of superposition can be expressed by addition too. Thus far, according to our today’s rules of arithmetic, we have to accept as true that

$$+1 + 0 = +1 \quad (23)$$

Exponentiation yields

$$(x_t)^{+1+0} = (x_t)^{+1} \quad (24)$$

Equation 24 changes slightly. In general, it is

$$(x_t)^{+1} \times (x_t)^{+0} = (x_t)^{+1} \quad (25)$$

□

As an example, the following Venn diagram (see [Venn, 1880, 1881](#)) exemplifies the theorem before but only insufficiently.

However, in order to put classical logic, number theory and other scientific disciplines on a foundation that can be verified by scientific experiments, the number 1 (see equation 3, p. 8) and number 0 (see equation 1, p. 8), for example, have been defined in natural constants. Inside equation 23, the number 0 has been superposed to the number 1 without any consequences. Equation 23 becomes

$$\left(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0\right) + \left(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0\right) - \left(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0\right) = \left(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0\right) \quad (26)$$

3.3. Theorem. Something divided by itself

Theorem 3 (Something divided by itself). *In general, it is*

$$(x_t)^{+0} = \frac{(x_t)^{+1}}{(x_t)^{+1}} \quad (27)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. It follows that

$$(x_t)^{+0} = (x_t)^{+0} \quad (28)$$

and that

$$(x_t)^{+0} = (x_t)^{+1-1} = \frac{(x_t)^{+1}}{(x_t)^{+1}} \quad (29)$$

□

Remark 3.1. *Assuming generality of the equation 29, we obtain the following picture.*

Case : $(x_t) = 0$:

$$(x_t)^{+0} = (0)^{+0} = \frac{(x_t)^{+1}}{(x_t)^{+1}} = \frac{(0)^{+1}}{(0)^{+1}} \quad (30)$$

Case : $(x_t) = 1$:

$$(x_t)^{+0} = (1)^{+0} = \frac{(x_t)^{+1}}{(x_t)^{+1}} = \frac{(1)^{+1}}{(1)^{+1}} \quad (31)$$

Case : $(x_t) = \infty_t$:

$$(x_t)^{+0} = (\infty_t)^{+0} = \frac{(x_t)^{+1}}{(x_t)^{+1}} = \frac{(\infty_t)^{+1}}{(\infty_t)^{+1}} \quad (32)$$

3.4. Theorem. The identity of x

Theorem 4 (Identity of x). *In general, it is*

$$(x_t) = (x_t)^{+1} \quad (33)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. We obtain

$$(x_t) = (x_t) \quad (34)$$

However, it is the same x_t which can be seen from the point of view of exponentiation or expressed in the language of exponentiation. Under these circumstances, it is equally true that

$$(x_t) = (x_t)^{+1} \quad (35)$$

However, can we reassess the truth or accuracy of this assumption? Nonetheless, we are prepared to give up the relationship of equation 35 completely, if the same relationship yields a contradiction. Rearranging equation 35, it is

$$\log(x_t) = \log(x_t)^{+1} \quad (36)$$

where \log denotes the logarithm (see [Nepers, 1614](#)), the inverse operation to exponentiation. In general, equation 35 is true, because

$$\log(x_t) = 1 \times \log(x_t) = \log(x_t) \quad (37)$$

□

3.5. Theorem. Something divided by itself

Theorem 5 (Something divided by itself). *In general, it is*

$$\frac{(x_t)}{(x_t)} = (x_t)^{+0} \quad (38)$$

Proof by direct proof. According to theorem 4, it is

$$(x_t) = (x_t)^{+1} \quad (39)$$

Dividing equation 39 by (x_t) , it is

$$\frac{(x_t)}{(x_t)} = \frac{(x_t)^{+1}}{(x_t)} = \frac{(x_t)^{+1}}{(x_t)^{+1}} = (x_t)^{+1-1} = (x_t)^{+0} \quad (40)$$

□

3.6. Theorem. The identity of x

Theorem 6 (Identity of x). *In general, it is*

$$(x_t)^{+l} = (+1)^{+l} \times (x_t)^{+l} \quad (41)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. We obtain

$$(x_t) = (x_t) \quad (42)$$

However, in our understanding and from the point of view of exponentiation, it is equally true that

$$(x_t)^{+1} = (+1)^{+1} \times (x_t)^{+1} \quad (43)$$

However, it may be appropriate to reassess again this assumption. Again, we are prepared to give up the relationship of equation 43 if the same yields a contradiction. Rearranging equation 43, it is

$$(+1) \times \log(x_t) = ((+1) \times \log(+1)) + ((+1) \times \log(x_t)) \quad (44)$$

where \log denotes the logarithm (see [Nepervs, 1614](#)), the inverse operation to exponentiation. In general, equation 43 is true, because

$$\log(x_t) = 0 + (1 \times \log(x_t)) = \log(x_t) \quad (45)$$

□

3.7. Theorem. The identity of x

Theorem 7 (The identity of x). *There are circumstances where*

$$(x_t)^{+0} = (+1)^{+l} \quad (46)$$

is true.

Proof by direct proof. Under conditions of axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$, the relationship

$$+1 + 0 = +1 \quad (47)$$

is equally true and equation 46 becomes

$$(x_t)^{+1+0} = (x_t)^{+1} \times (x_t)^{+0} = (x_t)^{+1} \quad (48)$$

According to theorem 6, equation 41, equation 48 becomes

$$(x_t)^{+1+0} = (x_t)^{+1} \times (x_t)^{+0} = (x_t)^{+1} = (1)^{+1} \times (x_t)^{+1} \quad (49)$$

or

$$(x_t)^{+1} \times (x_t)^{+0} = (+1)^{+1} \times (x_t)^{+1} \quad (50)$$

After application of an appropriate operation, equation 50 becomes

$$(x_t)^{+0} = (+1)^{+0} \quad (51)$$

□

In the case $(x_t) = +1$ it would follow that $+1^{+0} = +1^{+0}$.

3.8. Theorem. One power zero I

Theorem 8 (One power zero I). *In general, it is valid that*

$$(1)^{+0} \neq (+1)^{+1} \quad (52)$$

Proof by modus ponens. Everyone attentive reader certainly knows that the structure of modus ponens is given as **if** the

$$\text{premise (P) = true} \quad (53)$$

then the

$$\text{conclusion (C) = true} \quad (54)$$

In point of fact, in the course of the further investigation, P is found (by experiments et cetera) to be true. Therefore C must also be true. This structure of modus ponens is more or less a well-known fact, confirmed by scientific evidence. However, due to a combination of various (even exceptional) circumstances it is for sure to be kept in mind that the premise

$$+0 \neq +1 \quad (55)$$

is true. Therefore, the conclusion

$$(1)^{+0} \neq (+1)^{+1} \quad (56)$$

is also true. □

Based on equation 56, it is

$$(1)^{+0} + y = (+1)^{+1} \quad (57)$$

while

$$y = (1)^{+1} - (+1)^{+0} \quad (58)$$

3.9. Theorem. One power zero II

According to theorem 8, we must accept that $+1^{+0} \neq +1^{+1}$. However, in nature, i. e. something like a path of a falling ball which is straight might equally be at the same time curved too (see Barukčić, 2019, pp. 134-136) too. In other words, things, processes or even numbers describing these entities et cetera might depend upon the point of view (i. e. relative velocity v between two observers et cetera) of an observer too (**relativity of numbers**). Therefore, theorem 8 need to be re-investigated.

Theorem 9 (One power zero II). *It is true that*

$$(+1)^{+I} = (+1)^{+I} \times (+1)^{+0} \quad (59)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 2 or

$$+1 = +0 \quad (60)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false (see equation 56) that

$$(+1)^{+1} = (+1)^{+0} \quad (61)$$

However, the contradiction of equation 56 can be corrected. In other words, there is an unknown something, at this place denoted as x , potentially a kind of negation, which is able to correct this error. It is

$$(+1)^{+1} = (x) \times (+1)^{+0} \quad (62)$$

The value of x can be specified as $(+1)^{+1}$. In this case, equation 62 becomes

$$(+1)^{+1} = (x) \times (+1)^{+0} = (+1)^{+1} \times (+1)^{+0} = (+1)^{+1+0} = (+1)^{+1} \quad (63)$$

□

Equation 63 has several logical implications. In general, we must accept that

$$(+1)^{+1} = (+1)^{+1} \times (+1)^{+0} \quad (64)$$

while it is equally true that $+1^{+0} \neq +1^{+1}$ (see equation 56). Equation 64 provides to some extent arguments to assume that $+1^{+0} = +1$. We would obtain $+1^{+1} = +1^{+1} \times (+1)^{+0} = (+1)^{+1} \times +1$.

3.10. Theorem. Something and its own other in general

To broaden our own view on objective reality in the best possible way, let us assume that $+1^{+1}$ is determined from the point of view of a co-moving observer while the same something is found to be (from the point of view of a stationary observer) $+1^{+0}$. In this particular view the same or identical

something is equally both, equivalent with itself and not equivalent with itself or different too. It is becoming apparent that a correction factor might be of use to achieve a kind of equivalence. In the case before, such a correction factor is itself $+1^{+1}$. However, equation 63 demands at the end that $+1^{+1} = +1^{+0} \times +1^{+1}$. Since something is identical with itself or $+1^{+1} = +1^{+1}$ we may have to be prepared to tolerate the possibility that $+1^{+0} = 1$. However, are we justified in believing that this relationship is valid in general?

Theorem 10 (The superposition of 1). *We have some slight reason to believe that*

$$x_t^{+0} = +1^{+0} \quad (65)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. Under conditions, where

$$+1 = +1 + 0 \quad (66)$$

is true, it is equally true that

$$x_t^{+1} = x_t^{+1+0} = x_t^{+0} \times x_t^{+1} \quad (67)$$

while x might denote something, including zero and infinity. Today's rules of mathematics require us to accept that (see equation 43)

$$(1 \times x_t)^{+1} = 1^{+1} \times x_t^{+1} = x_t^{+1} \quad (68)$$

Up to now, we have not a single piece of verifiable evidence that equation 68 is false. Consequently, based on equation 68, equation 67 becomes

$$x_t^{+1} = x_t^{+0} \times x_t^{+1} = 1^{+1} \times x_t^{+1} \quad (69)$$

Dividing equation 69 by the term x_t^{+1} (see equation 8 and equation 40), it is

$$\frac{x_t}{x_t} = \frac{x_t^{+1}}{x_t^{+1}} = \frac{x_t^{+0} \times x_t^{+1}}{x_t^{+1}} = \frac{1^{+1} \times x_t^{+1}}{1^{+1} \times x_t^{+1}} = (1)^{+0} \times (x_t)^{+0} = (1 \times x_t)^{+0} = (x_t)^{+0} \quad (70)$$

Equation 70 treated as generally valid would be valid even under circumstances where $(x_t) = +1$. Under these assumptions, equation 70 becomes

$$(x_t)^{+0} = \left((x_t)^{+1} \right)^{+0} = \left((x_t)^{+0} \right)^{+1} = (1)^{+0} \quad (71)$$

□

At this very moment we have to point out the possible consequences of the general validity of the theorem 10. For the case that $x_t = 0$, we obtain the following result. It is

$$0^{+0} = \frac{0^{+1}}{0^{+1}} \quad (72)$$

In the same sense, for the case that $x_t = \infty$ we get

$$\infty^{+0} = \frac{\infty^{+1}}{\infty^{+1}} \quad (73)$$

3.11. Theorem. Different aspects of unity

Theorem 11 (Different aspects of unity). *In general, it is*

$$(1^{+0})^{+1} = (1^{+1})^{+0} = 1^0 \quad (74)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+1 = +1 \quad (75)$$

is true. Therefore, it is equally true that

$$(+1) \times (+0) = (+0) \times (+1) \quad (76)$$

In other words, it is

$$1^{((+0) \times (+1))} = 1^{((+1) \times (+0))} = 1^0 \quad (77)$$

or

$$(1^{+0})^{+1} = (1^{+1})^{+0} = 1^0 \quad (78)$$

□

3.12. Theorem. Something power zero

Theorem 12 (Something power zero). *Thus far, there are convincing arguments which demand to us accept that the relationship*

$$(+x)^{+0} = (+1)^{+\ln(+x)} \quad (79)$$

is generally valid and true.

Proof by direct proof. Under conditions where axiom 1 or

$$+1 = +1 \quad (80)$$

is true, it is equally true that

$$(+x)^0 = (+x)^{+\ln(+x) - \ln(+x)} = \frac{(+x)^{+\ln(+x)}}{(+x)^{+\ln(+x)}} = \left(\frac{+x}{+x}\right)^{+\ln(+x)} = (+1)^{+\ln(+x)} \quad (81)$$

□

In the case $(x_t) = 1$, it is

$$(x_t)^{+0} = (x_t)^{+\ln(+x)} = (1)^{+\ln(+1)} = (1)^{+0} \quad (82)$$

4. Discussion

In general, our own attempts, experiments et cetera to understand certain properties of objective reality truly the way the same are culminate and reach sometimes their peak in the fact that it is necessary to consider especially contradictions of objective reality in a more differentiated manner and free all indoctrination. Naturally, even if the following attitude might appear somewhat exaggerated, contradictions as such seem to be an inseparable and determining part of objective reality as such. In other words and against all dogmatism, it is an open secret that the one and the same something is quite regularly at the same (period of) time equally both, itself and its own other. As an example, it is the same path of a falling ball which may, in some circumstances, be a straight line and equally curved or not a straight line and both is true at the same (period of) time (see Barukčić, 2019, pp. 134-136). It is therefore not surprising that it is possible to approach objective reality from different viewpoints and various perspectives to cope with such nature given ‘double-dealing’ in more detail. In this regard it should be noted that as far as mathematics in part or in whole refers itself to objective reality, the methods of mathematics should be able to describe objective reality and the contradictions of objective reality with a high degree of accuracy. We need to notice that contradictions are evidenced part (see Barukčić, 2020) of objective reality. For this reason and taking into consideration various epistemological aspects, it need not seem curious if there are contradictions to be found in mathematics as well but it is much more important how mathematics and other science are dealing with contradictions. To put it more simply, a number, i. e. +1, is that what it is, +1 is identical with itself. However, such a number does not exist for itself but is related to natural events or processes etc cetera. The same number +1 is seen from simple arithmetic’s and algebra. Nonetheless, the same number +1 seems to us to be rather different if described by division or by exponentiation (see table 1).

Table 1. The relativity of numbers.

		Equivalent	
		YES	NO
Identical	YES	$1=1$	$(+1)^{+1} \neq (+1)^{+0}$
	NO	$y = x$	$0 \neq 1$

From the point of view of exponentiation, it is

$$(+1)^{+1} = +1 \quad (83)$$

From the point of view of division, it is

$$(+1)^{+0} = \frac{(+1)^{+1}}{(+1)^{+1}} = +1 \quad (84)$$

In order to combine some of these aspects arithmetically (see equation 57) it appears to be necessary to consider that

$$(1)^{+0} + (\underline{1})^{+0} = (+1)^{+1} \quad (85)$$

while the anti number of $(1)^{+0}$, denoted as $(\underline{1})^{+0}$, is determined as

$$(\underline{1})^{+0} = (+1)^{+1} - (1)^{+0} \quad (86)$$

Normalising equation 85, it is

$$\frac{(1)^{+0}}{(1)^{+1}} + \frac{(\underline{1})^{+0}}{(1)^{+1}} = \frac{(1)^{+1}}{(1)^{+1}} = (1)^{+0} \quad (87)$$

Rearranging equation 87, it is

$$(1)^{+0} = \frac{(1)^{+0} \times (1)^{+1}}{(1)^{+1}} = (1)^{+1} \times \left((1)^{+0} - \frac{(\underline{1})^{+0}}{(1)^{+1}} \right) \quad (88)$$

5. Conclusion

Under particular and exceptional circumstances its has been found that

$$(1)^{+1} \neq (1)^{+0} \quad (89)$$

or that $(1)^{+1}$ and $(1)^{+0}$ are not equivalent but different. However, upon some specific further investigations it can appear appropriate to simplify complex issues and to rely, i.e. by an act of definition, on the identity (see table 1)

$$(1)^{+1} = (1)^{+0} = 1 \quad (90)$$

Nonetheless, to achieve logical consistency, it does appear necessary to consider these kind of contradictions in greater detail.

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Erratum

Unfortunately and despite all efforts, some misprints appeared in the previous publications. Some of these misprints have been brought up to date in this publication, as far as possible.

Private note

In a private E-Mail which reached me on Friday, December 9, 2022, Okoh Ufuoma, Bachelor of Engineering, Lecturer at Southern Maritime Academy, Uwheru, Ughelli, Nigeria, stressed the need to distinguish between identity and equivalence of numbers. In Ufuoma's understanding it is: 'I think $1 \times 1 = 1^1$ is not identical with 1; they are only equivalent. 'However, Ufuoma's position quoted appears to contradict the summary of table 1.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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